

Nitrogen availability in digestates from full-scale biogas plants following soil application as affected by operation parameters and input feedstocks

Jared Onyango Nyang'au^{a,*}, Peter Sørensen^a, Henrik Bjarne Møller^b

^a Department of Agroecology, Aarhus University, Blichers Allé 20, 8830 Tjele, Denmark

^b Department of Biological and Chemical Engineering, Aarhus University, Blichers Allé 20, 8830 Tjele, Denmark

ARTICLE INFO

Original content: [Data for nitrogen availability in digestates from full-scale biogas plants following soil application as affected by operation parameters and input feedstocks \(Original data\)](#)

Keywords:

Mineralisation
Anaerobic digestion
Fertiliser value
Optimisation
Net inorganic N release

ABSTRACT

Biogas operation parameters are usually optimised to enhance biogas yields while ignoring digestate quality. This study evaluated the effects of varying operation parameters and input feedstocks used in co-digestion with manure on digestate properties and N turnover in soil for 80 days. Net inorganic N release (% of N input) from digestates varied significantly ($p < 0.001$) due to their contrasting properties. Temperature, hydraulic retention time (HRT), manure type and input feedstocks significantly influenced soil inorganic N release. Animal slurry co-digested with energy crops had the highest average net soil inorganic N release at 67 %, while co-digestion with straw-based feedstock had the lowest at 56 %. Feedstock type greatly influenced the choice of digesting temperature and HRT, with most energy crop-based feedstocks digested at <50 days HRT. Digestate properties $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ /total N, C/N and total carbon concentration significantly influenced net inorganic N release in soil. A better understanding of the effects of biogas operation variables on nutrient availability and digestate fertilising properties could help design and optimise the anaerobic digestion process to increase biogas yields and N fertiliser value of the digestates.

1. Introduction

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a potential mitigation measure to reduce greenhouse gases (GHGs) from livestock manure while at the same time addressing resource depletion concerns by substituting mineral fertilisers (Møller et al., 2022). During AD, complex organic materials in manures are degraded in anaerobic conditions into both biogas (CH_4 and CO_2) and digestate. The resultant digestate is characterised by a higher plant availability of N than the original feedstocks, making it an improved substitute for synthetic fertilisers (Møller and Müller, 2012). Moreover, the organic matter in the biomasses is degraded during the biochemical reactions of AD, resulting in more stable digestates, which improves manure management during storage and application (Karupiah and Azariah, 2019).

The quality of the digestates and their fertilising value vary depending on the biogas plants' input feedstock and operation parameters (Feng et al., 2023; Guilayn et al., 2019). Several substrates are utilised as feedstock in anaerobic co-digestion with manure to increase biogas output and optimise the AD process (Moset et al., 2017; Sarker et al., 2019). Compared to other substrates, mono-digestion of manures typically results in relatively low biogas yield due to organic matter

degradation in the animal's digestive system and low dry matter content, rendering the AD process uneconomical. In countries such as Denmark, there has been an increasing focus and shift towards co-digestion of the manure with high dry matter substrates, such as straw-rich deep litter and straw to increase biogas production (Møller and Nielsen, 2016; Møller et al., 2022). The shift is further necessitated by the legislative limits on how much energy crops can be utilised in biogas production as input feedstock.

Typically, the choice of the feedstock is influenced by feedstock availability, biogas yield, process stability of the feedstock and financial incentives (Häfner et al., 2022). The use of different feedstock, combined with varying biogas plant operation parameters, may result in variability in the fertilising properties of the digestates (Nsair et al., 2020; Risberg et al., 2017). The variability in the digestate composition makes precise fertilisation challenging and acts as a barrier to using digestates to substitute mineral fertilisers (Dahlin et al., 2015).

The use of recalcitrant biomasses for optimised industrial biogas production, coupled with a limited residence time of the biomass in the digester, could lead to a digestate characterised by partially decomposed organic matter (Albuquerque et al., 2012). The high dry matter content in the resultant digestates potentially results in high ammonia

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: jn@agro.au.dk (J.O. Nyang'au).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biteb.2023.101675>

Received 8 August 2023; Received in revised form 19 October 2023; Accepted 22 October 2023

Available online 23 October 2023

2589-014X/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

volatilisation when digestate is surface applied due to reduced infiltration and extended exposure to air. Moreover, it potentially induces N immobilisation, limiting the digestates' fertiliser value in the short term (Webb et al., 2013). In addition, due to partially degraded organic matter, there is an increased risk of GHGs emissions from digestates during storage and field applications. This necessitates optimising the AD process where digestates could be better stabilised and organic N mineralised to increase crop availability. Optimisation could synergise GHGs mitigation and tighten the nitrogen cycle through improved organic N mineralisation. The AD process can be optimised by either incorporating a pre-treatment step of biomass, a post-treatment step for the digestates or by optimising the operation parameters of the biogas reactors.

Several operating parameters of the biogas plant, individually or in synchrony, influence the anaerobic digestion process (Meegoda et al., 2018; Nsair et al., 2020; Sarker et al., 2019). The general performance of biogas plant reactors and the degradability of the input feedstock will rely on how the operation parameters and variables are selected. Some critical variables in biogas plants include feedstock type, digestion temperature, hydraulic retention time (HRT), reactor type, pH, organic loading rates and inhibitory components. HRT is one of the critical operation parameters of the biogas reactors affecting the quality of the digestate regarding mineralisation of the nutrients. It represents the average residence time of the substrate in the digesters, and it significantly affects the reactor's flow of nutrients, products, and unreacted substrates, thereby affecting the reactor's stability and performance. The effect of HRT on substrate degradation depends on the substrate's degradation potential, with the most significant effect achieved in recalcitrant biowastes. However, it is worth noting that extending HRT beyond a certain period might not necessarily enhance further substrate degradation due to inherent recalcitrance (Nyang'au et al., 2022).

Digestion temperature is another crucial parameter in an AD reactor. Temperature influences microbial activity, rate of hydrolysis, degree of biomass degradation, solubilisation of the nutrients and provides some level of sanitation to the digestates (Rahman et al., 2022). Two temperature regimes are typical for AD: mesophilic (25–45 °C) or thermophilic (45–60 °C). Mesophilic digestion is associated with a slower degradation rate and less biogas production at a certain retention time, meaning that mesophilic digestion requires a longer retention time to have a specific degradation of organic matter compared to thermophilic. However, it remains attractive due to its lower heat energy consumption than thermophilic reactors (Meegoda et al., 2018). On the contrary, thermophilic digestion is characterised by a faster degradation rate of the substrates due to a conducive environment for microbial and enzymatic degradation. The enhanced degradation rate of the substrates and improved hydrolysis step provide a higher organic loading rate possibility (Hartmann and Ahring, 2006). The temperature has a variable effect on the ultimate substrate degradability and, hence, digestate quality depending on other operation parameters and the nature of the substrate.

Several studies have evaluated the effects of the variation of the operation parameters of the biogas plant with the sole purpose of biogas yield optimisation as reviewed by Meegoda et al. (2018), Nsair et al. (2020) and Sarker et al. (2019). However, there is scarce information on how these operation parameters and various input feedstocks influence the fertilising properties of the digestates, i.e. NH_4^+ /total N, pH, C/N ratio and dry matter content, as well as their N turnover in soil following application. Evaluating how these operation parameters and different feedstocks influence N fertilising properties of digestates and ultimate nutrient turnover in the soil is crucial towards an integrated approach to optimisation of the AD process, where higher biogas yields and high availability of desired nutrients are prioritised. In this study, the effects of digestion temperature, HRT, manure type and input feedstocks of selected full-scale biogas plants were evaluated on a) the digestates' physico-chemical properties, b) on the net inorganic N release in the soil following digestate incorporation and c) the relationship between

physico-chemical properties of digestates and net inorganic N release as a fraction of added total N.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample collection

Digestates for this study were collected from 21 full-scale biogas plants in Denmark between November 2021 and April 2022. The samples were collected from the final process of the biogas plants, homogenized and divided into two portions. The collected samples were transported to Aarhus University, Research Centre Foulum biogas plant, Denmark, where they were stored at -18 °C until the start of the experiment. The first portion was used to evaluate the residual methane potential of the digestates, while the second portion was used for this study, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

The sampled biogas plants provide a good cross-section of the variations in Danish biogas plants regarding biomass composition and selected operational parameters, as presented in Table 1. The digestion temperature of the sampled biogas plants was either in the mesophilic (35–45 °C) or thermophilic range (46–55 °C). Six biogas plants operated at mesophilic conditions, while 15 operated at thermophilic conditions. The HRT of the digesters varied from 30 to 130 days (Table 1). The input feedstock utilised by the biogas plant included straw, deep litter, energy crops and industrial wastes, all co-digested with animal slurry. Eleven biogas plants had straw as one of their input feedstock with or without deep litter, while 10 had energy crops purely as their primary input feedstock co-digested with animal slurry. Most biogas plants with straw and deep litter as input operated at longer HRT, while those with only energy crops operated at HRT < 40 days (Table 1). Based on the major feedstock types, the digestates were classified into three main classes, i. e. those derived from mainly energy crops as main feedstock, those with straw and deep litter as part of their input feedstock and those derived from the straw without deep litter as part of their input feedstock. All the sampled biogas plants were fed with industrial wastes except for the biogas plant which D6 was sourced from. Industrial waste typically contains either one or a combination of slaughterhouse waste, glycerol from vegetable oil, fish waste, olive waste, molasses, whey from dairies or potato waste.

The main livestock manures utilised for the co-digestion in the sampled biogas plants were cattle and pig slurries. The pig slurry was used as the only manure input for biogas plants D11, D13 and D15, while the rest had a combination of pig and cattle slurries at different proportions (Table 1). Generally, the input materials to digesters were composed, on average with, a 75 % slurry and 25 % of feedstocks by wet weight.

2.2. Soil used for incubation experiment

The soil used for the incubation experiment was collected from the top 0–20 cm plough layer from an arable field at Aarhus University, Research Centre Foulum, Denmark (56°30'N, 09°35'E) in March 2022. The soil is a loamy sand containing 83 g clay kg^{-1} , 284 g silt kg^{-1} , 610 g sand kg^{-1} , 31 g organic matter kg^{-1} , 15.6 g total C kg^{-1} , 1.3 g total N kg^{-1} and pH (1:2.5 H₂O) of 6.18. The soil has properties representing average agricultural soils in Denmark. The soil was air-dried for a week and then sieved through a < 2 mm sieve to remove stones and larger plant residues. The soil was then homogenized, moistened and pre-incubated at 10 °C until the start of the experiment.

2.3. Soil incubation experiment

The digestates from the biogas plants were amended to the soil in an incubation experiment to study their N dynamics and availability. Approximately 50 g of the soil based on the dry matter weight was weighed into a 250 ml polyethylene bottle, and then the digestates were

Fig. 1. Schematic flowchart of the study. HRT = hydraulic retention time in days.

Table 1

Anaerobic digestion temperatures ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), hydraulic retention times (HRT) in days, total biogas reactor volumes (m^3) and input feedstock of the selected full-scale biogas plants. All sampled biogas plants were operated continuously.

Sample codes*	HRT days	Temperature $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Reactor total volumes $\times 1000 \text{ m}^3$	Feedstocks type				Manure type
				Energy crops [†]	Straw	Deep litter	Industrial waste	
D1	30	52	27.3	+	–	–	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D2	30	52	19.8	+	–	–	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D3	38	38	16.5	+	–	–	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D4	40	52	27.3	+	–	–	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D5	40	51	54.0	+	–	+	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D6	48	35	17.2	+	–	–	–	Cattle + pig slurry
D7	50	52	4.5	–	+	+	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D8	60	52	62.6	–	+	+	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D9	60	52	84.6	–	+	+	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D10	60	52	47.5	–	+	+	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D11	60	50	5.4	–	+	+	+	Pig slurry
D12	60	43	33.1	+	–	–	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D13	60	42	6.7	–	+	–	+	Pig slurry
D14	68	39	27.4	+	–	–	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D15	70	52	12.4	–	+	+	+	Pig slurry
D16	70	43	25.2	+	–	–	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D17	75	51	23.9	–	+	–	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D18	80	46	30.5	–	+	+	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D19	100	50	8.7	–	+	+	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D20	100	47	14.4	–	+	–	+	Cattle + pig slurry
D21	130	50	20.3	–	+	+	+	Cattle + pig slurry

Energy crops[†] = include either maize, grass, grass fibres, sugar beets, or maize silage. Sample codes* = the order of the samples (D1 - D21) is based on the increasing hydraulic retention times in the sampled biogas plants.

added at the rate of 200 mg N kg^{-1} soil, followed by another 50 g equivalent of dry soil to cover the digestates. A non-amended soil was included as a control treatment, and soil applied with ammonium sulphate at 100 mg N kg^{-1} soil rate was used as a reference treatment.

The application rate of the digestates is equivalent to 180 kg N ha^{-1} , assuming a 7-cm layer of soil is affected by the organic addition in the field (Sørensen et al., 2003). Water was added to each bottle to achieve a moisture level equivalent to 55 % of the water holding capacity (WHC), optimal for microbial activity and just low enough to limit denitrification. The bottles were covered with hole-pierced parafilm to prevent high water loss through evaporation while ensuring aeration throughout the incubation period. Each treatment was replicated 18 times to allow three replicates to be destructively sampled for analysis on days 0, 2, 7, 14, 32 and 80, giving a total of 414 samples. The samples were incubated at $10 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a dark room, representing the average, typical soil temperatures in spring under field conditions in Denmark after digestates/manures are applied.

The soil moisture content was monitored every two weeks and re-adjusted based on the initial weights. On each sampling day, the soil was removed from the polyethylene containers and homogenized in aluminium trays, and portions of 25 g were extracted with 100 ml of 1 M KCl by mechanical shaking for a half-hour (end-over-end) for inorganic N ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ and exchangeable $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$) analysis. Extracts were frozen at $-18 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until analyses. Soil pH (in soil extracts) and soil moisture content were measured on each destructive sampling day.

2.4. Analytical methods

Total nitrogen in the digestates was analysed according to APHA (2005) by the Kjeldahl digestion method (Kjeltec™ 8400, Foss Analytical CO. LTD, Denmark). Ammonium-nitrogen was analysed using an automated distillation-titration method (Sommer et al., 1992) using a Gerhardt Vapodest 10s distillation apparatus (Bonn, Germany). Sample preparation for fibre analysis entailed drying the samples at $60 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 48 h and grinding them to 0.8 mm particle size using Cyclotec™ 1093 mill (Foss, MN 55344, USA). The acid detergent fibre (ADF), acid detergent lignin (ADL) and neutral detergent fibre (NDF) were analysed to determine the hemicellulose, cellulose, lignin and neutral detergent soluble fibre (NDSF) contents as described by Van Soest et al. (1991), using a Foss Fibertec 2010 System (Foss Analytical CO. LTD, Denmark). Hemicellulose was calculated as the difference between NDF and ADF, cellulose as the difference between ADF and ADL; the lignin content was assumed to be equivalent to ADL, and NDSF was estimated as $(100 - (\text{NDF} + \text{ash content}))$.

The inorganic N ($\text{NO}_3^- \text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2^- \text{-N}$ and exchangeable $\text{NH}_4^+ \text{-N}$) in soil extracts was analysed by Auto Analyzer AA500 flow colourimetry (Seal Analytical GmbH, Germany). Total carbon content was analysed by Dumas combustion method using an elemental analyzer (Vario MAX Cube, Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH). Dry matter and volatile solids in digestates were analysed using standard methods (APHA, 2005).

2.5. Calculations

The net inorganic N release in the soil (% of N applied) from the digestates was estimated as the difference between the total inorganic N (TIN) in the amended soils with digestates and control soils without any amendment divided by total applied N (TN) in the digestates according to Eq. (1).

$$\text{Net inorganic N release (\% of N input)} = \frac{TIN_{\text{Treatment}} - TIN_{\text{control}}}{TN_{\text{Applied}}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Nitrous oxide and denitrification losses of N from the soils were assumed to be negligible or similar from all the treatments after digestate incorporation. Clay fixation of ammonium-N was equally assumed to be negligible. Net inorganic N mineralisation after 80 days of incubation was calculated as the difference in the net inorganic N release (NiNrelease) at day 80 and net inorganic N release at day 0 divided by applied organic N, as shown in Eq. (2).

$$\text{N mineralisation (\%)} = \frac{NiN_{\text{release}_{\text{day } 80}} - NiN_{\text{release}_{\text{day } 0}}}{\text{applied organic N}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

2.6. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was carried out in R statistical software version 4.0.3. Differences between digestates based on their net inorganic N release throughout the incubation period were tested by analysis of variance (ANOVA). A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was used for all statistical tests. Shapiro-Wilk tests, quantile-quantile plots and visual examination of the residuals against the fitted values were performed to confirm normality and homoscedasticity assumptions in all dependent variables. In cases where data deviated from the normal distribution, it was log-transformed. Posthoc analysis to identify digestates significantly different from each other was performed using the *emmeans* package. Pearson's correlations (r) between various physico-chemical properties of digestates, operation parameters of the digestates and net inorganic N release in the soil after 80 days of incubation were assessed with *cor()* function in R.

To evaluate the effects of digestion temperature, hydraulic retention time, input feedstock and type of manure on the net inorganic N release, a linear mixed effect model (*lmer*) within the *lme4*-package was used. Temperature, hydraulic retention time, input feedstock and type of manure were treated as fixed effects, while various biogas plants were treated as a random effect. The digestion temperature was divided into two categories, either mesophilic or thermophilic. The hydraulic retention time was treated as a continuous variable, while the input feedstocks class were categorised as either energy crops, straw with deep litter or straw without deep litter based on the proportion co-digested with livestock manure in the biogas reactors. The livestock manures were either pig slurry alone or a mixture of cattle and pig slurry. Anova type 3 was used to test the effect of the fixed factors in the model, and where interaction was not significant, this was dropped from the model. The best-fitting model was reached based on the models' likelihood ratio test. The final model is summarised in Eq. (3).

$$Y_{ijklm} = \mu + T_i + H_j + F_k + M_l + R_m + e_{ijklm} \quad (3)$$

where Y_{ijklm} is the net inorganic N release (% of N input) after 80 days of digestate incorporation, μ is the overall mean net N release, T is the temperature ($I = 1-2$), H is the continuous variable representing hydraulic retention time ($j = 30-130$), F is the feedstock type ($k = 1-3$), M is the manure type ($l = 1-2$), R is the random effect in biogas plants ($m = 1-21$), and e_{ijklm} is the residual error. The normality of residuals was checked by the quantile-quantile plots, while deviations of the model from the linear range were checked by Pearson's residues versus fitted values plot. Satterthwaite's function of *lmerTest* was used to calculate the degrees of freedom in the model.

3. Results

3.1. Physico-chemical characteristics of the digestates

The physico-chemical characteristics of the digestates are summarised in Table 2. The digestates had a variable dry matter content ranging from 3.1 to 10.8 %, with an average of 7.7 ± 1.90 % of FM. The DM content of digestates tended to increase with longer hydraulic retention times ($r = 0.46$, $p = 0.010$), majorly associated with the digestion of straw and deep litter feedstocks. The digestates had near neutral to slightly alkaline pH, with an average pH of 7.91 ± 0.22 . The digestates' pH tended to decrease with an increase in digestion temperatures and increase with an increase in the residence time of the biomass in the biogas reactors (Table 2, Fig. 2).

Total N in the digestates differed based on the input feedstock, with an average of 0.46 ± 0.09 % N of fresh matter. Digestate D16, with grass, maize and industrial waste as input feedstock, had the lowest total N content of 3.14 g N kg^{-1} , while digestate D8, with straw and deep litter as key input feedstock, had the highest total N content of 6.99 g N kg^{-1} (Table 2). The average $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ /total N ratio in the digestates, which could be used to predict plant available N in the first year of digestate application, was 61 ± 6.5 % (of total N), ranging from 49.8 % in D20 to 74.8 % in D16. The $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ /total N ratio correlated moderately negatively with the dry matter content in the digestates ($r = -0.45$; $p = 0.014$), total carbon content ($r = -0.51$; $p = 0.002$), digestion temperature of the reactors ($r = -0.45$; $p = 0.016$) and HRT ($r = -0.45$; $p = 0.013$).

The total carbon content of the digestates correlated strongly and positively with dry matter contents in the digestates ($r = 0.90$, $p < 0.001$), and it ranged from 13 to 39 g C kg^{-1} of fresh matter, with an average of $25 \pm 6 \text{ g C kg}^{-1}$ (Table 2, Fig. 3). The total carbon content was moderately positively correlated with hydraulic retention time ($r = 0.61$, $p < 0.001$). The C/N ratio in the digestates ranged from 3.7 to 9.0. The C/N ratio was moderately positively correlated with digestates' dry matter content ($r = 0.51$; $p = 0.001$), HRT of biogas plants ($r = 0.51$; $p = 0.002$) and the total carbon content in the digestates ($r = 0.71$; $p < 0.001$) (Table 2, Fig. 2).

The fibre composition of the digestates varied based on the operation parameters of the biogas plants and input feedstock. Hemicellulose, the easily degradable component of the substrates, was the lowest compared to cellulose and lignin (Table 2). Cellulose content was moderately positively correlated with dry matter content in digestates ($r = 0.60$; $p < 0.001$) and total carbon content ($r = 0.63$; $p < 0.001$). The neutral detergent soluble fibre (NDSF), which represents the soluble components in the digestate, moderately correlated with $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ /total N in the digestates ($r = 0.46$; $p = 0.010$), while it correlated negatively with the dry matter content ($r = -0.64$; $p < 0.001$) and total carbon content ($r = -0.68$; $p < 0.001$) in the digestates from the sampled biogas plants (Fig. 2).

3.2. Nitrogen turnover in the soil

The soil inorganic N dynamics and turnover were followed for 80 days after digestates application. Generally, there were significant differences in the net inorganic N release to the soil related to total N input and net N mineralisation related to organic N input among the digestates (Fig. 3, Table 3). A significant increase of $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content ($p < 0.001$) was observed immediately after digestate incorporation into the soil relative to the control, with the highest $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content observed in digestates D6, D15 and D16 ranging from 130 to $140 \text{ mg NH}_4^+\text{-N kg}^{-1}$ while lowest levels were observed in D8, D17 and D20 ranging from 90 to $108 \text{ mg NH}_4^+\text{-N kg}^{-1}$ dry soil. At the beginning of the incubation, the predominant form of inorganic N in the soils was $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$, while $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ was in low concentrations. The net $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ release from digestates started to decrease steadily after seven days of incorporation, while that of $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ gradually increased from an average of $10.2 \text{ mg N kg}^{-1}$ soil to

Table 2Physico-chemical characteristics of the digestates used in a soil incubation experiment. Values correspond to means \pm standard deviations.

Sample code	Dry matter	Volatile solids	pH	Total N	NH ₄ ⁺ -N	Total C	C/N	Hemicellulose	Cellulose	Lignin	NDSF*
	% of FM	% of DM		% of FM	% of total N	% of FM	ratio	% of DM	% of DM	% of DM	% of DM
D1	7.3 \pm 0.06	66.4 \pm 0.24	7.70	0.442	58	2.2 \pm 0.07	5.0	9.58	15.68	10.44	61.85
D2	6.0 \pm 0.06	72.5 \pm 0.28	7.91	0.389	66	2.2 \pm 0.10	5.6	6.65	14.80	14.44	62.46
D3	6.5 \pm 0.05	66.7 \pm 0.15	7.88	0.513	65	2.0 \pm 0.08	3.9	11.35	14.72	10.57	61.21
D4	6.0 \pm 0.06	66.4 \pm 0.29	7.06	0.443	63	2.1 \pm 0.08	4.6	6.73	16.82	13.96	60.49
D5	8.1 \pm 0.01	68.2 \pm 0.03	7.95	0.470	58	2.2 \pm 0.07	4.6	4.85	19.12	17.71	55.92
D6	9.0 \pm 0.12	72.4 \pm 0.27	8.01	0.444	68	2.6 \pm 0.18	6.0	11.15	16.99	14.68	53.73
D7	6.2 \pm 0.03	76.6 \pm 0.18	7.76	0.320	57	1.9 \pm 0.12	5.8	6.87	19.40	23.84	48.44
D8	10.3 \pm 0.02	74.8 \pm 1.50	8.06	0.699	56	3.5 \pm 0.05	5.0	13.42	20.71	17.28	45.99
D9	9.2 \pm 0.04	74.2 \pm 0.17	8.09	0.504	56	3.0 \pm 0.06	6.0	9.02	21.27	16.19	51.15
D10	7.0 \pm 0.01	68.2 \pm 0.02	7.96	0.481	59	2.1 \pm 0.11	4.3	17.82	7.57	11.26	61.13
D11	5.8 \pm 0.03	67.9 \pm 0.26	7.98	0.498	69	1.9 \pm 0.06	3.9	7.39	14.92	17.67	58.15
D12	7.2 \pm 0.04	62.5 \pm 0.27	7.97	0.449	64	2.1 \pm 0.14	4.7	8.18	12.53	9.09	69.35
D13	3.1 \pm 0.05	67.5 \pm 0.63	8.16	0.352	65	1.3 \pm 0.02	3.7	11.41	9.69	10.21	63.45
D14	9.2 \pm 0.08	70.5 \pm 0.25	7.9	0.411	61	2.7 \pm 0.00	6.6	13.56	15.79	11.54	56.76
D15	10.1 \pm 0.04	82.0 \pm 2.01	8.07	0.611	66	2.7 \pm 0.09	4.5	7.29	15.52	19.49	55.88
D16	7.3 \pm 0.10	74.4 \pm 0.35	7.98	0.314	75	2.8 \pm 0.02	9.0	10.06	17.08	15.66	55.03
D17	10.2 \pm 0.09	77.4 \pm 0.02	7.89	0.479	51	3.6 \pm 0.09	7.5	12.47	19.19	12.06	54.38
D18	6.6 \pm 0.09	71.0 \pm 0.29	8.03	0.460	62	2.2 \pm 0.02	4.7	4.56	14.18	16.69	62.65
D19	8.8 \pm 0.04	70.8 \pm 2.99	7.97	0.520	55	2.7 \pm 0.05	5.1	3.67	19.10	19.64	55.03
D20	8.0 \pm 0.12	73.8 \pm 0.27	7.96	0.452	50	3.0 \pm 0.03	6.6	10.80	18.34	17.34	51.11
D21	10.8 \pm 0.08	76.2 \pm 1.97	7.90	0.449	52	3.9 \pm 0.01	8.6	7.28	18.40	20.61	51.13
Mean	7.74	71.46	7.91	0.462	61	2.5	5.5	9.24	16.28	15.26	56.89
Std dev	1.90	4.67	0.22	0.09	6.5	0.64	1.47	3.46	3.42	3.96	5.74

FM = Fresh matter, DM = dry matter, NDSF* = Neutral detergent soluble fibre.

an average of 148 mg N kg⁻¹ soil after 80 days of incubation (Fig. S1).

After two days of decomposition in soil, the net inorganic N release in the soil (% of applied N) decreased with most of the digestates while it increased in some, i.e. D2, D3, D6, D7, D11–13, D16 and D20 (Fig. 3). After day 2, some treatments had a gradual increase in net inorganic N release in the soil until day 80 of incubation, while others (D2, D10, D14 and D18) showed a decline until day 7 followed by a gradual increase till the end of incubation. A continuous decrease in net inorganic N release was observed in digestates D15 and D21 till day 32, followed by a gradual small increment till day 80 (Fig. 3, Table 3). The inorganic N gradually increased in the control soil until the end of incubation, indicating soil organic N mineralisation (Table 3).

After 80 days of incubation, the net inorganic N release in soil (% of N input) from digestates was significantly different ($p < 0.001$), ranging from 49 to 74 % (of total N input), with an average of 63 % of N input. Digestates D20 and D21 had the lowest net inorganic N release of <50 % of N input, while digestates D3, D11 and D16 had the highest net inorganic N release in the soil of >70 % of N input (Fig. 3, Table 3).

Net N mineralisation (% of applied organic N) was observed in all the treatments after 80 days of incubation except for digestates D14 and D21, where there was net immobilisation of inorganic N. The highest N mineralisation was observed from digestates D3, D4, D8, D11, D15 and D16 at >20 % of applied organic N input (Table 3). The organic N mineralisation tended to increase with an increase in the concentration of total N in the digestates (Fig. 2). Adding digestates to the soil increased the soil pH by 0.96 pH units on average compared to the control at day 0. However, after 80 days of incubation, the soil pH applied with digestates was, on average, 0.21 pH units lower than that of the control (Table S1).

3.3. Effect of digestion temperature, hydraulic retention time (HRT), manure and feedstock type on net inorganic N release in the soil

The digestion temperature of biowastes in the sampled biogas plants significantly affected the net inorganic N release from digestates incorporated into the soil ($p = 0.029$). Digestion of feedstock at mesophilic temperatures resulted in a higher net inorganic N release in the soil (68.6 % of total N input) than for thermophilic temperatures (61.4 % of total N input). The choice of the variable digestion temperatures among

the biogas plants may be influenced by many factors, among them variable input feedstocks. For instance, biogas plants with energy crops as primary input feedstock were operated at either mesophilic or thermophilic temperatures, whereby digestion at mesophilic conditions resulted in a significantly higher net inorganic N release in the soil than at thermophilic temperatures. Biogas plants with straw and deep litter as part of their input feedstocks were generally operated at thermophilic temperatures, while those with straw without deep litter as part of their input feedstocks were operated at either mesophilic or thermophilic temperatures (Table 1).

The residence time of the biowastes in the biogas reactors, as linked to hydraulic retention time (HRT), significantly influenced the net inorganic N release (% of total N applied) in soil from the digestates ($p = 0.017$). Most digestates derived from energy crops-based feedstock had an HRT of <50 days, while those with straw-based feedstock had HRT of >50 days (Table 1). Digestates with HRT of >100 days, which mainly had straw and slurry as the major input feedstock, had the lowest net inorganic N release in the soil at the end of the 80 days of incubation (Tables 1, 3). In general, an increase in the HRT of the biowastes in the digesters did not increase the net inorganic N release in soil ($r = -0.59$; $p < 0.001$). An increase of HRT for straw-based feedstock with deep litter and straw-based feedstock without deep litter as input feedstock did not result in an increase in the net inorganic N release in soil, as exhibited by negative correlation coefficients of $r = -0.60$; $p < 0.001$ and $r = -0.93$; $p < 0.001$, respectively. However, for digestates derived from energy crops, an increase in HRT of biowastes in the biogas digesters tended to positively increase the net inorganic N release in soil (Fig. 2).

Different input feedstock to biogas plants significantly influenced the net inorganic N release from the digestates in the soil ($p = 0.014$). Digestates derived from a co-digestion with energy crops had the highest net inorganic N release at 67 % (of total N input), followed by those from a co-digestion with straw and deep litter feedstocks at 62 % (of total N input), and lastly, from a co-digestion with straw-based feedstock without deep litter, the average net inorganic N release of 56 % (of total N input). It is worth noting that energy crops-based feedstocks were generally digested at lower HRT, while straw-based ones were digested at relatively longer HRT. There was a positive synergistic effect between feedstock type and HRT on the net inorganic N release in the soil.

Fig. 2. Correlation's scatterplot matrix for digestates physico-chemical properties, net inorganic N release (Nrel) as % of added N, net N mineralisation (Nmin) as % of added organic N, digestion temperature (°C) and HRT (days) of the biogas plants. Pearson's correlation coefficients were estimated from a pairwise comparison of variables. The size and intensity of the circle's colour reflect the correlation's strength. The blue circles represent a negative correlation, while the red circles represent a positive correlation. The colour intensity indicates the strength of the correlation. Hem = hemicellulose (% of DM), Cell = cellulose (% of DM), Lig = lignin (% of DM), NDSF = neutral detergent soluble fibre (% of DM), TC = total carbon (% of FM), DM = dry matter (%), TN = total nitrogen (% of FM), C/N is expressed as a fraction and NH₄⁺-N/total N as a %. For each scatterplot, the variable plotted on the y-axis is indicated in the same line on the right, while the variables plotted on the x-axis are indicated on the lower side in the same column. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Moreover, the choice of the kind of livestock manure type used in the co-digestion of the feedstocks in the selected biogas plants, either as pig slurry or a mixture of varying proportional of cattle and pig slurry, greatly influenced the net N release in the soil, with the highest net inorganic N release observed in pig slurry based digestates ($p = 0.012$).

3.4. Effect of digestate quality on the net inorganic N release in the soil

The digestates physico-chemical properties had a variable effect on the net inorganic N release in the soil after incorporation. The net inorganic N release was positively and significantly correlated with the NH₄⁺-N/total N ratio ($r = 0.90$; $p < 0.001$), demonstrating the strong influence of the NH₄⁺-N/total N ratio in the N fertilising properties of the digestates. As the NH₄⁺-N/total N ratio in the digestates increased in each of the digestates' classes based on the input feedstock, the net inorganic N release at the end of incubation similarly increased. For instance,

digestates D6, D11 and D16 with NH₄⁺-N/total N of >68 resulted in the highest net inorganic N release to the soil after 80 days. A C/N ratio in the digestates negatively and significantly influenced the net inorganic N release. The overall correlation of C/N to net inorganic N release among all digestates was $r = -0.42$ with a $p = 0.034$; however, the relationship varied based on the feedstock class. For example, in straw-based digestates, there was a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.86$, $p < 0.001$), whereas in energy crop-based digestates, there was no clear relationship ($r = 0.26$; $p = 0.225$).

Total carbon content was moderately negatively correlated with net inorganic N release ($r = -0.54$; $p < 0.001$), while dry matter content was negatively correlated but not significant ($r = -0.40$; $p = 0.060$). In contrast, the total nitrogen concentration in the digestates did not significantly affect the net inorganic N release in the soil (Fig. 3). The neutral detergent soluble fibres (NDSF) positively influenced the net inorganic N release after digestate incorporation ($r = 0.51$; $p < 0.001$).

Fig. 3. Net inorganic N release (% of N input) in soil amended with digestates sourced from different full-scale biogas plants with varying input feedstock, hydraulic retention times, and digestion temperatures. Net inorganic N release was calculated by subtracting inorganic N measured in unamended soil. The grouping is based on the increasing hydraulic retention time (HRT) from D1 to D21. Bars indicate standard errors ($n = 3$).

Table 3

Average inorganic N (mg N kg^{-1} soil) during the 80 days of incubation at 10°C and net N mineralisation (% of applied organic N) at the end of 80 days measured in soil amended with digestates from different full-scale biogas plants with different input feedstocks and operating at different hydraulic retention times and digestion temperatures. All digestates were applied at 200 mg N kg^{-1} soil. The control represents unamended soil. Values correspond to means \pm standard deviations ($n = 3$).

Treatments	Days after digestate application						Net N mineralisation
	0	2	7	14	32	80	
Control	10.3 \pm 0.4 a	10.6 \pm 0.1 a	10.7 \pm 0.1a	11.6 \pm 0.0 a	12.3 \pm 0.2 a	19.4 \pm 0.8 a	–
D1	119.6 \pm 6.2 cdef	116.5 \pm 3.7 bcd	127.5 \pm 2.9 defgh	126.4 \pm 2.7 fg	134.2 \pm 2.2 fg	144.8 \pm 1.0 ef	18.5 abcd
D2	136.6 \pm 9.2 fgh	131.9 \pm 3.5 defgh	136.3 \pm 5.6 ghij	133.2 \pm 3.5 ghj	140.2 \pm 2.2 gh	148.5 \pm 1.5 efgh	3.8 ab
D3	133.5 \pm 9.0 efgh	139.6 \pm 7.0 gh	137.5 \pm 1.6 hij	143.4 \pm 3.0 ijk	152.7 \pm 2.5 ijk	163.2 \pm 2.3 ij	30.5 bcd
D4	121.1 \pm 3.5 cdefg	133.6 \pm 5.0 defgh	136.9 \pm 0.3 hij	138.0 \pm 1.8 hij	146.3 \pm 0.4 hij	156.2 \pm 2.1 ghi	33.8 cd
D5	124.4 \pm 4.4 cdefg	119.9 \pm 10.5 bcdefg	128.7 \pm 2.4 defghi	130.7 \pm 3.0 gh	139.4 \pm 0.4 gh	147.1 \pm 0.1 efg	17.0 abcd
D6	134.0 \pm 2.8 fgh	135.2 \pm 5.1 defgh	142.5 \pm 6.2 ijk	143.9 \pm 2.8 hi	145.8 \pm 2.4 hi	156.1 \pm 2.5 ghi	19.7 abcd
D7	116.0 \pm 4.4 cde	115.6 \pm 1.1 bcde	118.7 \pm 7.5 bcd	119.2 \pm 3.0 de	120.0 \pm 2.5 de	131.5 \pm 3.4 c	7.4 abc
D8	113.8 \pm 8.2 cd	109.8 \pm 2.7 bc	121.7 \pm 4.6 bde	125.0 \pm 5.9 ef	128.2 \pm 0.9 ef	143.7 \pm 3.5 e	23.4 bcd
D9	120.7 \pm 2.7 cdefg	120.3 \pm 1.1 bcdefg	123.2 \pm 5.8 cdefg	124.4 \pm 1.2 f	129.2 \pm 1.3 f	141.2 \pm 3.2 de	12.6 abcd
D10	132.1 \pm 9.9 efgh	119.9 \pm 9.1 bcdefg	122.5 \pm 3.8 cdef	129.0 \pm 1.0 gh	139.7 \pm 3.7 gh	150.0 \pm 2.7 efgh	10.6 abcd
D11	130.7 \pm 2.6 defgh	143.1 \pm 7.6 h	148.9 \pm 1.5 jk	143.7 \pm 2.9 jk	156.2 \pm 0.7 jk	163.6 \pm 2.4 ij	38.3 d
D12	131.1 \pm 3.6 dh	138.7 \pm 2.6 fgh	137.3 \pm 0.3 hij	142.4 \pm 0.7 hijk	147.7 \pm 2.9 hijk	153.5 \pm 3.0 fghi	19.9 abcd
D13	136.5 \pm 1.4 fgh	137.7 \pm 5.3 efgh	141.5 \pm 3.1 hijk	136.8 \pm 2.1 hi	145.8 \pm 1.4 hi	150.0 \pm 2.1 efgh	6.3 abc
D14	138.2 \pm 5.2 gh	131.5 \pm 12.7 defgh	133.2 \pm 5.4 efghi	133.2 \pm 2.4 gh	140.4 \pm 1.3 gh	147.2 \pm 1.1 efg	–0.5 a
D15	127.7 \pm 5.3 cdefgh	128.4 \pm 11.9 cdefgh	135.0 \pm 0.2 fghij	140.3 \pm 5.0 hi	145.1 \pm 3.7 hi	157.4 \pm 6.8 hij	25.1 abcd
D16	147.4 \pm 10.3 h	149.5 \pm 2.1 h	154.6 \pm 3.2 k	158.6 \pm 1.9 k	157.3 \pm 2.9 k	167.6 \pm 2.3 j	21.5 abcd
D17	108.8 \pm 3.5 bc	107.6 \pm 5.9 b	108.7 \pm 7.3 b	111.6 \pm 1.7 cd	114.1 \pm 3.2 cd	127.3 \pm 1.4 c	9.7 abcd
D18	135.8 \pm 8.3 fgh	132.3 \pm 8.0 defgh	136.4 \pm 2.0 ghij	136.6 \pm 1.6 gh	140.0 \pm 5.3 gh	150.3 \pm 3.7 efgh	7.5 abc
D19	119.5 \pm 7.6 cdef	118.7 \pm 13.3 bcdef	119.6 \pm 2.1 bd	121.5 \pm 2.3 d	118.0 \pm 2.2 d	133.4 \pm 1.3 cd	5.4 abc
D20	98.0 \pm 1.8 b	106.4 \pm 4.3 b	109.6 \pm 3.6 b	103.5 \pm 2.4 bc	108.6 \pm 1.3 bc	117.3 \pm 1.1 b	10.2 abcd
D21	111.2 \pm 2.8 bc	110.7 \pm 3.2 bc	113.7 \pm 4.4 bc	103.5 \pm 0.2 b	105.1 \pm 0.2 b	116.5 \pm 1.5 b	–3.4 a
p-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001

Means followed by different letters within each column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

However, other digestates fibre components negatively influenced the inorganic N release in the soil. For instance, cellulose content was moderately negatively correlated with net inorganic N release after 80 days of incubation ($r = -0.43$; $p = 0.025$).

3.5. Prediction of the net inorganic N release from digestates based on the operation conditions of the biogas and input feedstock

The net inorganic N release in the soil was predicted based on the

estimated coefficients of a linear mixed model consisting of fixed and random effects (Table 4). The measured net inorganic N release in the soil correlated strongly with the model's predicted net inorganic N release ($r = 0.99$; $p < 0.001$). However, the model should only be used cautiously to predict plant-available N in digestates from other biogas plants and other soil types (Fig. 4). For instance, the measured net inorganic N release in the soil of three digestates reported by Nyang'au et al. (2022), depicted as A, B and C, were predicted and found to be within >90 % confidence interval based on the variable operation parameters of the biogas reactors and their input feedstocks (Fig. 4).

4. Discussion

4.1. Nitrogen turnover in the soil

Generally, there was a high net inorganic N release (% of total N input) in the soil from the digestates from the selected biogas plants. The high net inorganic N release could be linked to the mineralisation of organic N compounds in the biowastes to readily available NH_4^+ -N during anaerobic digestion (Moller and Muller, 2012). The observed variations in the net inorganic N release and net N mineralisation in the soil after 80 days of incorporation of the digestates could be explained by either the variable input feedstocks, contrasting biogas operation parameters and/or the variable physico-chemical properties of the digestates.

The type of organic manure and manure treatment technique significantly impact nutrient availability, soil microbial responses, and mineralisation potential of organic pools of applied digestates (Jedidi et al., 2004; Rigby and Smith, 2013). For instance, the selected variable digestion temperatures and HRT probably linked to input feedstock type in the studied biogas plants were expected to influence organic matter degradation differently, resulting in digestates with different properties and varying nitrogen fertiliser value equivalents. Besides that, following digestate application, the soil microbial activities are important for N-immobilisation and mobilisation, influencing the ultimate available N for plant uptake.

A temporal net inorganic N immobilisation was observed after incorporating some of the digestates between days 0 and 2, which could be linked to microbial assimilation of inorganic N for the synthesis of protein and other nitrogen-containing organic compounds associated with the decomposition of easily decomposable compounds like volatile fatty acids (Sørensen, 1998). Conversely, low quantities of decomposable organic matter may explain the lack of observed immobilisation during the same time (day 0–2) and the remainder of the incubation period for other digestates. This is indicative that most decomposable compounds were decomposed during the AD process, leaving only more stable compounds in the digestates.

The steady rise in inorganic N after day two may be attributed to the partial re-mineralisation of immobilised N and the organic N mineralisation of digestate in the soil, implying that soil microbes can decompose some organic compounds that the microbial community in the biogas anaerobic digesters could not decompose. On the contrary, the continuous decline of net inorganic N release in two digestates, D14 and D21, could probably be due to immobilisation by soil microorganisms during their growth, as evidenced by the relatively higher dry matter contents

Fig. 4. Measured net inorganic N release in the soil (% of added N) after 80 days of incubation versus predicted net inorganic N release based on the model regression equation from Table 4. The blue points A, B and C presents predicted net inorganic N release in soil (% of N input) of digestates based on the operation conditions and input feedstocks to the digestates whose net inorganic N release (% of N input) was measured and reported by Nyang'au et al., (2022). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

and volatile solids contents in the digestates.

The observed low mineralisation rates in most of the digestates after soil incorporation indicate that no significant changes in available N would be expected during the first months of decomposition. Therefore, if N losses are assumed to be negligible, the plant available N in the digestates may be comparable to the initial NH_4^+ -N in the digestates. As a result, to maximise nitrogen use efficiency from digestates, their application should be synchronised with plant uptake (Delin and Engstrom, 2010). With appropriate management strategies, the high proportion of available N in the digestates from anaerobic digestion could potentially replace more mineral fertilisers, reducing the cost of agricultural production and improving environmental sustainability.

The insignificant N mineralisation in some of the digestates may be explained by the anaerobic digestion process decomposing organic N compounds like proteins and rendering the remaining organic N pool resistant to further microbial degradation following soil application (Rigby and Smith, 2013). Conversely, the high mineralisation rates observed in a few of the digestates could probably be due to the presence of easily hydrolysable proteins in the digestates. These findings corroborate the findings of Jimenez et al. (2020), who also reported a high N mineralisation in the range of 18 to 30 % of added organic N in some of their digestates following a soil incubation for 12 weeks, which

Table 4

Estimation coefficients for net inorganic N release in the soil (as % of total N in digestate) based on the digestion temperature, hydraulic retention time and input feedstock to the biogas plants using multiple-component linear regression.

Response	intercept		Temperature		HRT		Feedstock		Manure
Log (net inorganic N release)	4.347	+	-0.095 if T 0 if M	+	-0.002 × HRT	+	-0.0074 if S -0.1460 if SX 0 if E	+	0.132 if PS 0 if CS_PS

T = thermophilic, M = mesophilic, HRT = Hydraulic retention time (days), S = straw + deep litter feedstock, SX = Straw without deep litter feedstock, E = energy crop-based feedstock, PS = pig slurry, CS_PS = mixture of cattle and pig slurry.

was linked to the degradability of the digestates.

The variable range of the net inorganic N release (% of the N input) in soil from the studied digestates is within the range reported by Nyang'au et al. (2022), who reported a net inorganic N release in the soil in the range of 52 to 62 % of the total N input of digestates sourced from different biogas reactors with varying HRT and input feedstocks. The similar trends of net N release from digestates based on their nutrient composition are depicted in the nitrogen fertiliser replacement values (NFRV) when the digestates are field applied. For instance, when Nyang'au et al. (2023) applied the same digestates used in the incubation experiment to winter wheat and spring barley in a field experiment, they observed the same trends of plant N availability, with differences among the crops explained by the timing and method of digestate application.

4.2. Effect of digestion temperature, hydraulic retention time (HRT), manure and feedstock type on net inorganic N release in the soil

Several challenges, such as process complexity, poor stability, inefficient biodegradability, substrate complexity, and low productivity, limit the AD process from being used to its optimal potential for methane production despite its rapid expansion and effectiveness in the treatment of wastes (Sarker et al., 2019). Thus, to optimise the AD process to achieve its full potential, its operation parameters ought to be studied and well understood. This study evaluated the effects of digestion temperature, hydraulic retention time, manure type and input feedstock on nutrient availability in digestates following soil application in order to understand how to effectively optimise operation parameters of biogas plants to achieve high nutrient availability in digestates and subsequently high net inorganic N release to the soil.

The temperature at which biowastes are digested affects microbial activity, rate of hydrolysis, degradation efficiency, substrate solubilisation and presence of pathogens in the digestates (Rahman et al., 2022). Optimisation of digestion temperature is crucial as increasing digestion temperatures may increase reaction kinetics and enzymatic activities, increasing the hydrolysis of soluble compounds in feedstocks and making them more accessible for microbial attack during AD. However, findings from this study indicate that digestates from mesophilic digestion temperatures (35–45 °C) had a higher net inorganic N release in soil than digestates from thermophilic digestion temperatures (50–55 °C). A reason for these unexpected findings could be that digestion temperature is linked to other biogas operation configurations and parameters that could affect the release of nitrogen, such as residence time of the biowastes in the reactor, pH, organic loading rates, mixing rates and the type of substrate (Ruile et al., 2015). Nevertheless, increasing digestion temperatures does not always guarantee positive benefits regarding the degradation kinetics of the biowastes, as it is associated with risks of process instabilities, especially when digesting nitrogen-rich substrates at higher organic loading rates (Angelidaki et al., 2005). High ammonia concentration from high nitrogen-rich substrates may cause ammonia inhibition, resulting in low biogas yields and nutrient solubilisation due to limited substrate degradation.

The higher net inorganic N release at mesophilic temperatures than thermophilic temperatures could also be linked to the selective choice of digestion temperature based on the feedstock type. For instance, the energy crop-based feedstocks with relatively higher nitrogen content than straw-based feedstock were generally digested at mesophilic temperatures, as they are easily decomposable. On the contrary, the straw-rich and deep litter-based feedstocks, whose resultant digestates had lower net inorganic N release, were generally digested at thermophilic temperatures, 50 to 55 °C, due to their lignocellulosic nature. This co-variation between feedstocks and digester configuration makes it difficult to determine the most important factors influencing N availability in the digestates.

The variability in the degradation efficiency among the feedstocks depends on the feedstock compositions, with some feedstocks being

recalcitrant to decomposition and some not (Tambone et al., 2010). The disparities in the feedstocks result in variations in the digestate physico-chemical properties such as C/N ratio, dry matter content and NH_4^+ -N/total N ratio, which significantly affects their fertiliser value, as seen in this study. Therefore, variable hydraulic retention times should be considered based on the inherent chemical components of the feedstock and their degradability during the anaerobic digestion process to achieve sufficient degradation of the feedstocks.

The observed high net inorganic N release from energy crop-based feedstocks could be explained by the fact that they degrade quickly in the biogas reactors, increasing surface area for microbial and enzymatic activities during AD, which enhances nutrient mineralisation. In addition, their incorporation into the soil may lead to further decomposition, increasing net inorganic N release into the soil. On the other hand, the lignocellulosic nature of straw and deep litter makes them resistant to microbial attack during AD, resulting in a digestate with less soluble nutrients and non-decomposed organic matter. Applying such digestates can induce microbial immobilisation, potentially reducing the N fertiliser value of the digestates, as observed in digestates D14 and D21. These results agree with previous studies by De Notaris et al. (2018), Fontaine et al. (2020) and Nyang'au et al. (2023), who reported a lower nitrogen fertiliser replacement value for digestates derived from straw and deep litter-based feedstocks than those derived from green manures and energy crops. Similarly, Häfner et al. (2022) reported variable nitrogen uptake and organic matter mineralisation among different digestates, attributed to the distinct feedstock composition of digestates.

The higher net N release from straw-based feedstock with deep litter than straw-based feedstock without deep litter may be explained by deep litter soaking and holding nutrient-rich liquids prior to AD, contributing to relatively higher N fertiliser value. Besides that, the significant effect of pig slurry on net inorganic N release compared to a mixture of pig and cow slurries could be attributed to easily degradable organic components in the pig slurry (Sørensen et al., 2011).

Hydraulic retention time (HRT) is a critical anaerobic digestion parameter whose selection should be carefully considered. Long HRT may not be economical for biogas plants as it reduces treatment capacity and increases operation costs, whereas short HRT is associated with washout of essential microorganisms responsible for substrate degradation, making the process ineffective (Ho et al., 2014; Nsair et al., 2020). The recalcitrant lignocellulosic feedstocks, such as straw and deep litter, could require relatively long HRT and appropriate pre-treatment steps to improve their degradation compared to energy crop-based feedstocks. Moreover, increasing HRT may potentially reduce residual methane potential as more biogas is recovered from substrates, reducing methane emissions during storage of digestates and improving revenues (Angelidaki et al., 2005). Extending HRT is hypothesized to positively influence nutrient mineralisation as the contact time between the substrate and responsible microbial and enzymatic activities increases. However, this study found a negative relationship between hydraulic retention time and net inorganic N release in the soil. This surprising effect could be linked to the feedstock quality.

Extending HRT for straw-derived feedstocks with and without deep litter did not increase net inorganic N release in soil. This could probably be explained by the fact that, despite increasing the residence time of biowastes in the reactor, the microbial community cannot further break down the feedstock components due to their recalcitrant nature. However, we observed a positive effect of HRT on net inorganic N release in the energy crop-based feedstocks. A study by Ruile et al. (2015) found that increasing HRT above 150 days did not result in any further degradation in the substrates, implying that no change in available N would be expected as organic N mineralisation might be limited due to recalcitrance.

The measured net N inorganic N release from digestates correlated well with the predicted values by the model. The net inorganic N release from digestates appeared to depend on the biogas operation parameters, input feedstock and digestates properties. Therefore, predicting the

plant available N from digestates should be possible based on selected variables and input feedstocks. For example, net N release from digestates assessed by Nyang'au et al. (2022) was comparable to the regression model estimates. The relationship between the digestion temperature, HRT and input feedstock with soil net inorganic N release demonstrates that provided operation parameters and input feedstock are known, plant available N in digestates may be predicted, albeit cautiously.

4.3. Relationship between digestate quality and the net inorganic N release in the soil

Most of the digestates exhibited a high NH_4^+ -N/total N ratio, low C/N ratio, low dry matter content, and alkaline pH, which may be related to transformations during anaerobic digestion (Møller and Müller, 2012). The variable modes of operation of the biogas plants similarly produced digestates with a variable range of characteristics that affected their quality. The variability and ranges of the physico-chemical properties of the digestates utilised in this study are comparable to those of earlier studies (Cooke et al., 2023; Jimenez et al., 2020; Møller and Nielsen, 2016; Nyang'au et al., 2023; Tampio et al., 2016). The negative relationship between dry matter content with NH_4^+ -N/total N and net inorganic N release after 80 days of incubation could be attributed to the fact that high dry matter is associated with the use of large amounts of lignocellulosic feedstocks, which are generally low in N and result in a build-up of recalcitrant cellulose and lignin compounds. A similar trend was reported by Toft et al. (2022) in digestates collected from biogas facilities in Denmark over time with energy crops and straw as input feedstocks.

The significant correlations observed between digestate physico-chemical characteristics (i.e. NH_4^+ -N/total N, C/N, DM) and net inorganic N release in soil suggest that intrinsic digestate properties may be used to predict nitrogen fertiliser properties of the digestates. The high correlation between NH_4^+ -N/total N ratio and net inorganic N release, for example, implies that NH_4^+ -N/total N in the digestates could predict with certainty the net inorganic N release in the soil from the digestates and, as a result, plant available N in the first year of digestates application. These findings corroborate those of Nyang'au et al. (2022) and Fontaine et al. (2020), who found high correlations between digestates' NH_4^+ -N/total N and C/N contents with net inorganic N release in the soil in similar laboratory incubation experiments. Likewise, following digestate field application, high correlations were observed between some digestate intrinsic properties (NH_4^+ -N/total N, C/N, DM) and nitrogen fertiliser replacement values (Fontaine et al., 2020; Nyang'au et al., 2023).

4.4. Practical perspectives

The biogas industry is rapidly expanding, presenting new opportunities and challenges. For instance, in Denmark, there is a shift to replace or supplement energy crops with new biomasses such as straw and other agricultural residual products to meet the ever-increasing demand for renewable energy. Straw has considerable potential for biogas production, but its utilisation presents economic challenges, particularly when the proportion used is large. This transition necessitates re-configuration and re-design of biogas reactors to enhance degradation of the lignocellulosic biomasses for enhanced biogas production, i.e., through integrating a pre-treatment or a post-treatment step of the biomasses (Møller and Nielsen, 2016). Therefore, the anaerobic digestion process should be optimised to achieve stable and efficient biogas production from target input feedstocks. The optimisation may be accomplished by biogas design considerations with optimum operational parameters and incorporating appropriate biomass pre-treatment techniques prior to AD or a post-treatment step.

The focus on process optimisation in most full-scale biogas plants has been solely on improving biogas production and methane yield without

considering the quality of the resultant digestate. This may result in a digestate with poor fertiliser value, typically characterised by high dry matter content, high C/N ratio and low NH_4^+ -N/total N ratio. As a result, an integrated approach of biogas-digestate optimisation should be implemented to ensure the maximum benefits of the AD process, focusing on optimising the process for higher biogas and high availability of desired nutrients (Logan and Visvanathan, 2019). Therefore, the influence of each operation parameter and input feedstocks on the net inorganic N release must be evaluated to effectively design an AD process aimed at achieving higher nutrient availability in digestates meant for crop production while concurrently increasing biogas yields.

This study found significant effects of temperature, HRT, manure type and input feedstock on the net inorganic N release in the soil following digestates incorporation. Furthermore, strong relationships between operation parameters and digestate properties with net inorganic N release in soil were observed, which could be cautiously used to predict the plant available N in the digestates.

Considering that the input feedstock type was primarily linked to the digestion temperature and hydraulic retention times, the designs of biogas reactors and the selection of operating parameters should take the properties of the input feedstock into account in order to achieve a higher fertiliser value of the resultant digestates. Combining optimal operating conditions with a suitable feedstock pre-treatment technology prior to AD may even result in a superior digestate quality with higher fertiliser value (Nyang'au et al., 2023). The pre-treatment techniques may additionally increase the biogas yields and/or lower viscosity in the biogas reactor, allowing large quantities of lignocellulosic biomass to be handled. Further, the digestate quality could be improved by integrating a post-treatment technique such as digestate separation into solid-liquid fractions.

5. Conclusions

Different digestates from various biogas plants resulted in a variable net inorganic N release (% of N input) in the soil. The differences in net inorganic N release following soil incorporation of digestates were significantly influenced by the digestion temperature of the biogas digesters, hydraulic retention time (HRT), the manure type used, and input feedstocks utilised. The effects of temperature and HRT were further linked to the feedstock type. For instance, increasing HRT had a significant positive effect on the digestion of energy crop-based feedstocks, while increasing temperature in the digestion of straw/deep litter-based digestates had an insignificant effect on the net inorganic N release. Unexpectedly, higher net inorganic N release was observed at lower digestion temperatures, which could be related to more straw/deep litter-based feedstocks used at thermophilic conditions and energy crop-based feedstocks digested at mesophilic conditions.

The relationship between the digestion temperature, HRT, manure type and input feedstock with soil net inorganic N release reveals that, provided biogas operating parameters and input feedstock are known, plant available N in digestates could be predicted, albeit cautiously. Furthermore, the net inorganic N release from the digestates was strongly correlated with some of the digestate's physico-chemical properties, such as the NH_4^+ -N/total N ratio, C/N ratio, neutral detergent soluble fibres (NDSF) and total carbon content implying that they could also be used to predict available N in the digestates. Therefore, selecting biogas operation parameters based on the feedstock type and their synergistic effects could significantly improve and optimise the degradation kinetics of the feedstock, increasing N availability in the digestate and thus improving its nitrogen fertiliser value.

Funding

This work was funded by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 860127 (FertiCycle project). The authors acknowledge

funding from the Danish Green Development and Demonstration program (GUDP) for the “*Methods for reducing ammonia loss and increased methane yield from biogas slurry*”-MAG project (Project No. 34009-21-1829).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jared Onyango Nyang'au: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Peter Sørensen:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Henrik Bjarne Møller:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

All data is openly available online in a Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8397247>.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the technical staff at the Department of Agroecology and Department of Biological and Chemical Engineering, Aarhus University, for their technical assistance. We wish to also to acknowledge Dr. Maarit Mäenpää for her advice on statistical analysis.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biteb.2023.101675>.

References

- Alburquerque, J.A., de la Fuente, C., Ferrer-Costa, A., Carrasco, L., Cegarra, J., Abad, M., Bernal, M.P., 2012. Assessment of the fertilizer potential of digestates from farm and agroindustrial residues. *Biomass Bioenergy* 40, 181–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2012.02.018>.
- Angelidaki, I., Boe, K., Ellegaard, L., 2005. Effect of operating conditions and reactor configuration on efficiency of full-scale biogas plants. *Water Sci. Technol.* 52 (1–2), 189–194. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2005.0516>.
- APHA, 2005. *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*, 21 ed. American Public Health Association, Washington DC, USA.
- Cooke, J., Girault, R., Busnot, S., Morvan, T., Menasseri-Aubry, S., 2023. Characterising the effect of raw and post-treated digestates on soil aggregate stability. *Waste Biomass Valor* 14 (9), 2977–2995. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-023-02045-3>.
- Dahlin, J., Herbes, C., Nelles, M., 2015. Biogas digestate marketing: Qualitative insights into the supply side. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 104, 152–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2015.08.013>.
- De Notaris, C., Sørensen, P., Møller, H.B., Wahid, R., Eriksen, J., 2018. Nitrogen fertilizer replacement value of digestates from three green manures. *Nutr. Cycl. Agroecosyst.* 112 (3), 355–368. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-018-9951-5>.
- Delin, S., Engstrom, L., 2010. Timing of organic fertilizer application to synchronise nitrogen supply with crop demand. *Acta Agr. Scand. B-S P* 60 (1), 78–88. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09064710802631943>.
- Feng, L., Aryal, N., Li, Y.Q., Horn, S.J., Ward, A.J., 2023. Developing a biogas centralised circular bioeconomy using agricultural residues-challenges and opportunities. *Sci. Total Environ.* 868, 161656. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.161656>.
- Fontaine, D., Feng, L., Labouriau, R., Møller, H.B., Eriksen, J., Sørensen, P., 2020. Nitrogen and sulfur availability in digestates from anaerobic Co-digestion of cover crops, straw and cattle manure. *J. Soil Sci. Plant Nut.* 20 (2), 621–636. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42729-019-00151-7>.
- Guilayn, F., Jimenez, J., Martel, J.L., Rouez, M., Crest, M., Patureau, D., 2019. First fertilizing-value typology of digestates: a decision-making tool for regulation. *Waste Manag.* 86, 67–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.01.032>.
- Häfner, F., Hartung, J., Möller, K., 2022. Digestate composition affecting N fertilizer value and C mineralisation. *Waste Biomass Valor* 13 (8), 3445–3462.
- Hartmann, H., Ahring, B.K., 2006. Strategies for the anaerobic digestion of the organic fraction of municipal solid waste: an overview. *Water Sci. Technol.* 53 (8), 7–22. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2006.231>.
- Ho, D., Jensen, P., Batstone, D., 2014. Effects of temperature and hydraulic retention time on acetotrophic pathways and performance in high-rate sludge digestion. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48 (11), 6468–6476. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es500074j>.
- Jedidi, N., Hassen, A., van Cleemput, O., M'Hiri, A., 2004. Microbial biomass in a soil amended with different types of organic wastes. *Waste Manag. Res.* 22 (2), 93–99. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X04043930>.
- Jimenez, J., Grigatti, M., Boanini, E., Patureau, D., Bernet, N., 2020. The impact of biogas digestate typology on nutrient recovery for plant growth: accessibility indicators for first fertilization prediction. *Waste Manag.* 117, 18–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.07.052>.
- Karuppiath, T., Azariah, V.E., 2019. *Biomass pretreatment for enhancement of biogas production. Anaerobic digestion* 150, 111509.
- Logan, M., Visvanathan, C., 2019. Management strategies for anaerobic digestate of organic fraction of municipal solid waste: current status and future prospects. *Waste Manag. Res.* 37 (1_suppl), 27–39. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X18816793>.
- Meegoda, J.N., Li, B., Patel, K., Wang, L.B., 2018. A review of the processes, parameters, and optimization of anaerobic digestion. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 15 (10), 2224. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15102224>.
- Moller, K., Muller, T., 2012. Effects of anaerobic digestion on digestate nutrient availability and crop growth: a review. *Eng. Life Sci.* 12 (3), 242–257. <https://doi.org/10.1002/elsc.201100085>.
- Møller, H.B., Nielsen, K.J., 2016. Biogas Taskforce – developing and streamlining biogas production in Denmark, DCA-National Center for Food and Agriculture. Denmark, pp. 1–125. <https://dca.pub.au.dk/djfpublikation/djfpdf/DCARapport077.pdf>.
- Møller, H.B., Sørensen, P., Olesen, J.E., Petersen, S.O., Nyord, T., Sommer, S.G., 2022. Agricultural biogas production—climate and environmental impacts. *Sustain. Basel* 14 (3), 1849. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031849>.
- Moset, V., Fontaine, D., Moller, H.B., 2017. Co-digestion of cattle manure and grass harvested with different technologies. Effect on methane yield, digestate composition and energy balance. *Energy* 141, 451–460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.08.068>.
- Nsair, A., Cinar, S.O., Allassali, A., Abu Qdais, H., Kuchta, K., 2020. Operational parameters of biogas plants: a review and evaluation study. *Energies* 13 (15), 3761. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13153761>.
- Nyang'au, J.O., Moller, H.B., Sorensen, P., 2022. Nitrogen dynamics and carbon sequestration in soil following application of digestates from one- and two-step anaerobic digestion. *Sci. Total Environ.* 851 (Pt 1), 158177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158177>.
- Nyang'au, J.O., Moller, H.B., Sorensen, P., 2023. Effects of electrokinetic and ultrasonication pre-treatment and two-step anaerobic digestion of biowastes on the nitrogen fertilizer value by injection or surface banding to cereal crops. *J. Environ. Manage.* 326 (Pt A), 116699. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116699>.
- Rahman, M.A., Moller, H.B., Saha, C.K., Alam, M.M., 2022. The effect of temperature on the anaerobic co-digestion of poultry droppings and sugar mill press mud. *Biofuels-Uk* 13 (2), 139–147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17597269.2019.1649902>.
- Rigby, H., Smith, S.R., 2013. Nitrogen availability and indirect measurements of greenhouse gas emissions from aerobic and anaerobic biowaste digestates applied to agricultural soils. *Waste Manag.* 33 (12), 2641–2652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2013.08.005>.
- Risberg, K., Cederlund, H., Pell, M., Arthursen, V., Schntner, A., 2017. Comparative characterization of digestate versus pig slurry and cow manure - chemical composition and effects on soil microbial activity. *Waste Manag.* 61, 529–538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2016.12.016>.
- Ruile, S., Schmitz, S., Monch-Tegeder, M., Oechsner, H., 2015. Degradation efficiency of agricultural biogas plants - a full-scale study. *Bioresour. Technol.* 178, 341–349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2014.10.053>.
- Sarker, S., Lamb, J.J., Hjelme, D.R., Lien, K.M., 2019. A review of the role of critical parameters in the design and operation of biogas production plants. *Appl. Sci.-Basel* 9 (9), 1915. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9091915>.
- Sommer, S.G., Kjellerup, V., Kristjansen, O., 1992. Determination of total ammonium nitrogen in pig and cattle slurry - sample preparation and analysis. *Acta Agric. Scand. Sect. B Soil Plant Sci.* 42 (3), 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09064719209417969>.
- Sørensen, P., 1998. Carbon mineralization, nitrogen immobilization and pH change in soil after adding volatile fatty acids. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 49 (3), 457–462. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2389.1998.4930457.x>.
- Sørensen, P., Weisbjerg, M.R., Lund, P., 2003. Dietary effects on the composition and plant utilization of nitrogen in dairy cattle manure. *J. Agric. Sci.* 141 (1), 79–91. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859603003368>.
- Sørensen, P., Mejnertsen, P., Møller, H.B., 2011. Nitrogen Fertilizer Value of Digestates from Anaerobic Digestion of Animal Manures and Crops. In: NJF seminar 443. Utilization of manure and other residues as fertilizers. Falköping, Sweden. NJF Report Vol 7 no 8, 42–44. <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/20269/>.
- Tambone, F., Scaglia, B., D'Imporzano, G., Schievano, A., Orzi, V., Salati, S., Adani, F., 2010. Assessing amendment and fertilizing properties of digestates from anaerobic digestion through a comparative study with digested sludge and compost. *Chemosphere* 81 (5), 577–583. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2010.08.034>.
- Tampio, E., Salo, T., Rintala, J., 2016. Agronomic characteristics of five different urban waste digestates. *J. Environ. Manage.* 169, 293–302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2016.01.001>.

- Toft, L.V., Juul, T.A., Larsen, S.U., Hjort-Gregersen, K., Møller, H.B., 2022. Use of straw in biogas plants, Report prepared for Danish Energy Agency., pp. 1-81. https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Bioenergi/221006_brug_af_halm_i_biogasanlaeg.pdf.
- Van Soest, P.J.J.B., Robertson, Lewis, B., 1991. Method, for dietary fiber, neutral detergent fiber, and non Starch polysaccharides in relation to animal nutrition. *J. Dairy Sci.* 74, 3583. [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(91\)78551-2](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(91)78551-2).
- Webb, J., Sørensen, P., Velthof, G., Amon, B., Pinto, M., Rodhe, L., Salomon, E., Hutchings, N., Burczyk, P., Reid, J., 2013. An assessment of the variation of manure nitrogen efficiency throughout Europe and an appraisal of means to increase manure-N efficiency. In: *Advances in Agronomy*, vol. 119. Elsevier, pp. 371–442. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-407247-3.00007-X>.